

**A STUDY ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION
STRATEGIES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN RURAL
HOUSEHOLDS OF UTTAR PRADESH**

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ABSTRACT

This research project investigates how commercial banks in rural areas of Uttar Pradesh are implementing strategies to promote financial inclusion. The study relies on both primary and secondary data sources, employing quantitative and qualitative research methods to gather information from a sample of rural households and commercial banks in the region. The research identifies the challenges faced by commercial banks in implementing their strategies, and explores the potential benefits of financial inclusion through surveys of rural households and discussions with bank officials. The project aims to enhance the effectiveness of commercial banks' strategies by offering practical recommendations to policymakers and commercial banks. Overall, this research contributes to the existing literature on financial inclusion and provides insights for promoting financial inclusion in rural areas of Uttar Pradesh.

Keywords : Financial Inclusion, Commercial Banks, Rural Areas, Financial Literacy, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Financial inclusion entails guaranteeing equitable availability of banking and financial services to every individual in society, without any form of discrimination, thereby ensuring equal access for all. Its primary goal is to provide basic financial services to every person, without considering their income or savings. The primary objective of financial inclusion centers around to offer reliable financial solutions to economically disadvantaged groups, promoting fairness and transparency in the provision of financial assistance, free from any forms of inequality or hidden costs.

The microfinance sector plays a crucial role in Uttar Pradesh (UP) by offering tailored financial solutions to uplift the living standards of the underprivileged. UP ranks among the top five states in terms of a substantial gross loan portfolio amounting to Rs. 33.91 billion, with an impressive annual growth rate of approximately 69.9%. The state is served by 17 prominent microfinance institutions (MFIs) with 820

branches, including Margdarshak, Sonata, Utkarsh, Fusion, Disha, and Cashpor. For a detailed overview of performance indicators, please refer to Table-3 in the SLBC-UP agenda for June 2015.

A. Coverage of Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY)

As part of the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), banks have opened a staggering 17.74 crore accounts with deposits exceeding 22,000 crores. To ensure widespread access to banking services, more than 1.26 lakh Bank Mitras equipped with online devices capable of e-KYC account opening and interoperable payment facilities have been deployed. Moreover, banks have organized 1,31,012 Mega Financial Literacy camps and established 89,876 Financial Literacy counters to promote awareness about PMJDY and the utilization of RuPay cards. Financial literacy training has been provided to 1,47,418 students in educational institutions. Over 10 lakh accounts are eligible for the Overdraft facility, of which 1,64,962 account holders have availed

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this facility. Furthermore, successful claims have been processed for 847 life cover policies (Rs. 30,000) and 389 accident insurance cover policies (Rs. 1 lakh). For comprehensive details on the status of Uttar Pradesh, please refer to Table-4 in the SLBC-UP agenda for June 2015.9 services. These individuals may be unaware of the existence and functions of banks, or they may face obstacles in accessing banking services due to not meeting the minimum eligibility criteria set by banks. Such criteria may include minimum income requirements, credit scores, age restrictions, and work experience. Consequently, many of these individuals, often unemployed and lacking education, resources, or funds, are unable to meet these criteria and secure banking services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As stated by **Massey (2010)**, the importance of financial institutions in the progress of financial inclusion within a developing country cannot be emphasized enough. The government's efforts to encourage the growth and promotion of financial inclusion can be greatly enhanced through the active participation of capital market players, including financial institutions. These institutions play a crucial and extensive role in facilitating the achievement of financial inclusion objectives.

In **Tamilarasu's (2014)**, study, the crucial role of financial inclusion in attaining inclusive growth was emphasized. The focus was specifically on examining the involvement of the banking sectors in promoting financial inclusion. The study highlighted the necessity for India, considering its significant rural population predominantly involved in agriculture, to ensure the provision of banking and financial services to every individual in a manner that is unbiased, clear, and fair, while still being affordable. Furthermore, the study underscored the importance of establishing an effective mechanism to distribute resources in all directions as a key facilitator for fostering the expansion of financial inclusion.

Sachdeva (2015) conducted a study to analyze the role of public sector banks in promoting financial inclusion. The focus of the research was specifically on

investigating the impact of the "Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojna" initiative, which aims to provide financial services to all regions of the country. Sachdeva argued that the successful accomplishment of financial inclusion hinges on the existence of efficient mechanisms and robust governance within the banking sector.

Birla (2016) conducted a study examining the involvement of commercial banks in promoting financial inclusion within the Indian economy. The study revealed that financial inclusion plays a vital role in the economic progress of developing countries like India. To achieve inclusive growth, the Indian government has implemented various schemes with the objective of integrating the unbanked segment of society. Commercial banks play a significant part in this process through the establishment of new branches, particularly in rural areas, introduction of appealing investment opportunities, provision of financial education centers, and expansion of ATM accessibility.

These endeavors aim to attract a greater number of individuals to actively participate in the banking and financial system.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the influence of Commercial Banks and measures implemented by the Government of India and Reserve Bank of India (RBI) to foster financial inclusion.
2. The aim was to assess the effective implementation of financial inclusion strategies by commercial banks in rural areas of Uttar Pradesh..

Strategies of Commercial Banks in rural areas of U.P. to promote FI :

The subsequent responsibilities are to be undertaken by commercial banks as part of the financial inclusion program-

- A) Financial literacy
- B) Credit counselling
- C) BC/BF model
- D) KYC norms
- E) KCC/GCC
- F) No-frill accounts
- G) Branch expansion
- H) Mobile banking:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

A research design refers to the organization of factors involved in gathering and analysing data in a way that effectively aligns with the research objective while being efficient in its approach. It serves as the underlying framework for conducting research. In this case, the research design focused on providing a detailed description of the subject matter.

Descriptive research : Descriptive research is a type of research methodology that aims to describe and explain the characteristics, behaviours, and phenomena of a particular subject or population. It involves observing, documenting, and analyzing data to provide an accurate and detailed depiction of the topic under investigation.

Sampling design:

The following factors have been determined as part of the sample design-

Area of Sampling - The area of Sampling was nearby region of Gorakhpur which are semi-urban and rural.

Sample Size : A minimum number of respondents were selected from different areas within the Gorakhpur zone for the sample. The sample size was set at 100.

Sampling Technique : The sampling method used was Non-Probability Sampling, specifically Purposive Sampling. The primary objective was to target specific attributes within a population that are of interest and would provide the most suitable answers to the research questions. The individuals who responded to the questionnaire were people of rural areas and town as well as employees of banks.

Sources of data collection : The source of data collection is both Primary and Secondary. For the collection of primary data, Questionnaire is used which is a primary data collection tool which comprises of a set of questions that aims to collect information from the respective respondents. On the other hand, secondary data was obtained from various sources such as websites, books, and journals.

Tools of Presentation

To make the data easily understandable and meaningful, various tools such as tables and graphs were utilized in this research for data presentation.

Tools of Analysis

In this research the data analysis procedure was done by the various tools of the MS-Excel which are table, percentage, diagrams, Graphs or Pie-charts.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

Demographic Characteristics

Gender		Profession		Literacy		Income	
Male	74	Farmer	37	Illiterate	37	Less than 50000	43
Female	26	Business	14	5 th	18	50000 – 1 Lakh	22
Source: Primary data (Computed)		Job (daily wages)	28	10 th	21	1 Lakh – 5 Lakhs	24
		Other (Student)	21	Graduate	24	Above 5 Lakhs	11

1. In your opinion, what can the commercial bank do to improve its strategies of financial Inclusions in rural areas of Uttar Pradesh?

	No. of Respondent	Percentage of respondent
Increase in number of branches	27	27%
Increase in number of ATMs	8	8%
Financial Awareness	51	51%
Improve the quality of customer services	14	14%
Total	100	100%

Table No. 1: Source – (Primary data)

Interpretation

From the analysis of above data, it is clear that majority of the respondents about 51% were in favor of increasing the financial awareness of bank, 14% want

improvement in quality of customer service in the bank, 27% and 8% of the respondents have suggested to increase the number of branches and ATMs.

2. Do you think any awareness camp or financial literacy programmes are organized by banks in your area?

	No. of Respondent	Percentage of respondent
Yes	33	33%
No	62	62%
Don't Know	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Table No. 2: Source – (Primary data)

Interpretation

From the above graph it is clear that most of the respondents are not aware of any awareness camp or

financial literacy programs organized by the banks in their areas.

3. What are the common challenges faced by commercial banks when implementing strategies to promote financial inclusion in rural areas?

	No. of Respondents	Percentage of respondents
Lack of awareness about financial services	26	26%
Lack of access to technology	5	5%
Lack of trust in the banking system	12	12%
All of the above	57	57%
Total	100	100%

Table No. 3: Source – (Primary data)

Interpretation

Based on the responses of most participants, common obstacles encountered by commercial banks in rural areas include limited knowledge about financial services, inadequate technological access, and a lack of confidence in the banking system.

FINDINGS

- State Bank of India (SBI) is the sole bank with extensive coverage in providing financial services across the entire nation.
- About 90% of SBI branches have deployed BCs in every village or town. BC outlets are increasingly becoming the means through which banking services are being made accessible in rural areas, particularly in regions that previously lacked such services.
- Majority of the respondents (62%) have accepted that there must be an arrangement of awareness

camp to educate customers and implement financial inclusion effectively.

- BCs and Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) has taken the financial inclusions to the last mile delivery in rural areas or unbanked region.
- The most common obstacles encountered by commercial banks in rural areas include limited knowledge about financial services, inadequate technological access, and a lack of confidence in the banking system.

SUGGESTIONS

- The government of India should expand the network of bank branches and must install ATMs onsite and offsite of the bank in villages as well as in remote areas.
- Banks ought to prioritize the creation of products that are straightforward, reasonably priced, and

provide substantial value to their customers.

- In order to understand their customers better and improve their services, banks should ensure that all forms and documents are available in the regional language of their customers.
- Banks should promote the importance of banking services to the public through advertising, financial literacy programs and financial inclusion campaigns to raise awareness.
- To comprehend the financial requirements of rural communities, banks should conduct periodic surveys in villages.
- Every bank in villages must establish a credit counselling centre to assist farmers and village residents in obtaining loans quickly and on time.

CONCLUSION

The effective implementation of financial inclusion strategies by commercial banks in rural areas of Uttar Pradesh is crucial for promoting economic growth and reducing poverty in the region. The study emphasizes the importance of financial literacy, credit counseling, the BC/BF model, KYC norms, KCC/GCC, no-frill accounts, branch expansion, and mobile banking as key areas of focus for commercial banks to achieve success in financial inclusion. Despite government initiatives, certain segments of society, including vulnerable groups, low-income households, and illiterate individuals, still face barriers to accessing financial services due to factors such as lack of awareness, financial literacy, interest, or banking habits. To address these challenges, banks can establish credit counseling centers and collaborate with NGOs to enhance their services and reach out to disadvantaged groups. Moreover, commercial banks can contribute significantly by opening new branches, introducing attractive investment schemes, establishing financial education centers, and expanding the ATM network to encourage greater participation in the banking and financial system, especially in rural areas.

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